

The Reflection of Patriarchal Culture in *Breaking Ties*

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Abstract:

The present research paper aims to focus on the issue of Muslim women and their subordinate status in the system of patriarchy. Cultural context and geographical location have a strong impact on the status of Muslim women. The various traditions, Muslim clerics, patriarchy and culture play a commendable role in shaping the personality of Muslim women. The reflections of patriarchal culture and Arab tribal culture have played significant roles in the formation of religious norms. Traditionally women are treated as secondary and subordinate. Conservative people believe Muslim women have no role to play outside her home. Women are confined in four walls. Patriarchal Muslim community has its impact on the lives of Muslim women. Muslim women's liberation is seen as an attack on the orthodox dominance of Maulavi's, who are considered as the guard of Shariya.

Muslim women's identity is crushed under the influence of patriarchy. Though some Muslim women come forward to speak against the existing social structure, they are attacked and alienated. The teachings of Shariya are followed only from the male perspective. The concepts like Izzat and Sharum are observed in relation with women's chastity. The images of Muslim women are constructed with the help of male oriented reading of the Quran. The issue of veiling is also one of the pioneer reasons for making women subordinate. For many people veiling is the symbol of backwardness and ignorance. Even it draws a line between 'being a Muslim' and 'others'.

Keywords: Islam, Subordination, Gender Crisis, Patriarchy, Feminism, Veiling, Religious Norms and Culture.

Introduction:

Sara Abubackar was born in a Malayalam speaking family from Kasargod in 1936. She especially speaks about South Indian Muslim women and their experiences about multiple identities in multicultural society. Her stories narrate Muslim women's experiences which mainly speak about injustices in patriarchal society. She penned down the suppressed and silenced voices of Kannada Muslim women. The Muslim women are subordinated and suppressed by the orthodox patriarchal culture. She sincerely attempts to articulate the voice of countless Muslim women.

Feminism:

Throughout the different ages, patriarchy has underestimated the women's fundamental rights. Men consider women as subordinate and weak. Hence, women have to fight to get their sexual equality. Women's active protest against their subordinate status is called feminism. According to *Encyclopedia of Feminist Literary Theory*, "If feminism has always committed itself to fighting social and economic injustice, then there is a corresponding sense that the feminist study of literature has to explore the full range of female experiences across the globe. It has to understand not just what unites women across the

globe but what potentially divides them.” (Ed-Wallace: Introduction: XIX :1996)

Feminism has its root in the late eighteenth century. It started as a political movement which aimed for women's liberation. In this respect, the definition of feminism in the “Oxford Concise Dictionary of Politics” is rather noteworthy. “Feminism is a way of looking at the world, which women occupy from the perspective of women. It has its central focus on the concept of patriarchy, which can be described as a system of male authority, which oppress women through its social, political and economic institutions.” (Osborne: 2001: 8)

Thus, feminism moves around the unjust rules of patriarchy and social structure. Even Gayatri Spivak admitted that due to the burden of particular ideology women are not allowed to participate in the process of decision making. Hence, the feminist critics and the writers have started to demand equal status. Mary Wolstonecraft, Gayatri Spivak, Virginia Wolf, and Simon-De Beauvoir have strongly opposed the marginalization of women. They fought to get equal economic and social status for women. Kate Millett's *Sexual Politics* (1985) is the one of the pioneer books which has analyzed the power relations between men and women.

Feminist novelists focus on the protagonist's search for the "self." Thus, ‘Feminist novel’ mainly relates with the issues like gender discrimination and power relations. In the post-modern era feminist works are associated with the terms like Psycho analysis, Marxism and Deconstruction. Virginia Woolf handles various sociological issues while analyzing women's writing. In the 1960’s and 1970’s feminist criticism was related with “Images of Women Criticism.” It critically operates the role of literature which has given more preference to male dominance. This school has appealed to the readers to read the text from a “female point of

view.” The issue of literature and ideology was handled skillfully by the Marxist feminism. It is related to the complex relations between gender and the economy. In 1792, Mary Wollstonecraft strongly opposed the “misconceived representations of women as meek, obedient, passive and pretty.” (34) She objected that society remains passive to cultivate women's caliber. In the 1970’s French feminists Helene Cixous, Luce Irigaray and Julia Kristeva started to explore the new feminism style of writing. They argue that feminist language is real and fluid than masculine language. Thus, feminist critics have always opposed the images of ideal feminist like pretty, delicate, subordinate, submissive etc. They find out the gap between fact and representation Beauvoir's observation in this respect is remarkable. “Through her passivity she bestows peace and harmony-but if she dislikes this role. She is seen forthwith as praying mantis, and ogress. In any case, she is seen as the privileged other, through which the object fulfils herself. One of the measures of man, his counterbalance, his salvation, his adventure, his happiness.” (1993:262) Thus, she appeals to all human beings to come together and work hand in hand and abolish enslavement of women. The feminist critics aims to establish autonomous status for women. They strongly oppose the hierarchical structure; where women are obliged to be passive. Autonomy could be achieved through healthy conversation and relations with each other. Thus, feminism is the perfect tool to understand the operating system of women’s suppression and images.

Muslim Women:

Muslim women are controlled by *Shariya*. In the Muslim community, the patriarchal gender system is the major ruling power. Male domination, early marriage, preference to son, behavioral codes for women are keenly observed

in the Muslim community. These all issues are the product of male dominance. Muslim clerics interpret *Quranic* verses as per their male perspectives, whereas westernized philosophy estimates Muslim women as more subordinate and marginalized. Amina Wadud is the radical feminist. Her book *Quran and Quranic Verses (1999)* throws light on Islam and gender equality with the help of various sources in *Quran*. She claims that there is a need for new readings of the *Quran*.

Breaking Ties is the translation of Sara Abubakar's famous novel *Chandragiri Teeradalli*. The novel is related to the personal and social accounts of Muslim women. The story moves around Nadira, who fights against her egotistical father. The novel deeply criticizes issues like talaq and marital attack. This is the first novel by a Muslim woman writer in Kannada. *Breaking Ties* keeps alive the issue of personal politics. The personality of Nadira's father is not acceptable because of his uncompromising nature. Her mother has no right to raise voice against the injustices. It depicts disharmony and lack of communication under the roof of patriarchy.

Nadira, the daughter of Mohammad Khan and Fatima, married Rashid. Her husband Rashid stands as a fresh air in her life. Throughout her life, Nadira has watched her mother as being submissive on various issues. On such a background Rashid becomes a comfort zone for her. But her happiness is shattered by her wicked father who puts an issue of wedge between his daughter and her husband. Hence Nadira and her son are forcibly kept at his place. Her father decides to compound Nadira's misery by arranging her marriage to Selim, the most elderly and weary person. He does not consider Nadira's opinion. Her choice and feelings are crushed. He becomes responsible for the pathetic condition of Nadira. Thus, Nadira's father is described as the

most aggressive person, her husband is irrational and her mother is speechless. Thus, Nadira is surrounded by such a foolish person who always makes her life insecure.

Conclusion:

Breaking Ties discusses the lifestyle and attitude of Muslim women who are segregated from the mainstream by the course of a river. It projects the female body as the source of suppression and domination. At the opening of the novel, it is observed that Mohammad Khan is cruel in his behaviour. On the first night, he is totally brutal with his wife and even Maulavi's and other elders support him and not the worried child-wife. Nadira goes through the psychological trauma which scatters her mental hygiene. Mohammad Khan is responsible for ruining Nadira's life and dreams. He becomes the symbol of masculine superiority. *The Breaking Ties* analyses the major critical issues of Muslim community like talaq, polygamy and *Purdah*. Sara Abubakar focuses on the need of Muslim women's revolt against the outdated customs. She voiced for the feminine sensibility and marginalization of Muslim women. The novel expresses revolutionary thoughts against physical, sexual, economic and religious suppression. Female body is the major source of oppression. The novel strongly depicts the miserable condition of Muslim women caught between the rigid social and religious norms.

Muslim women's position in the society provides ample scope for argument and research. The understanding of Islam, Islamic social structure, the interpretation of Quranic verses, tribal traditions and culture all provides the perfect framework of various images of Muslim women.

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